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*Response to reviews and summary of revisions

Authors (A): All comments from Reviewer #2 were addressed. All suggestions of the Editorial Office were followed.

Reviewers' comments:
Reviewer #2:

R#2: The manuscript has been greatly improved and I really like the emphasis on error estimates. The results and conclusions are much clearer as well as the implications. I now think the manuscript is appropriate for RSE. My minor comments are below.

Abstract

R#2: Page 1, Line 12. Close space between sentences.

A: corrected

Page 2, Line 40. Is there a better word than "sensitive"? "pressing" maybe.

A: changed as suggested

R#2: Page 2, Line 52. Extra space after Lu 2006.

A: corrected

Page 14, Line 359 and 360. It might be my preference, but really best not to use "..is presented in Figure 6".

A: we have replaced "presented" with "shown"

References

R#2: Some of the references are not formatted correctly. Some use caps in the titles. Please correct for RSE.

A: reference were re-checked

=====

Comments from the Editorial Office:

EO: -- shorten your "Research Highlights" to 85 CHARACTERS or less per bullet point (count spaces between words as a CHARACTER)

A: length shortened

EO -- remove the boxes from around figures (i.e. Figure 2, Figures 4-7) - they are not necessary

A: boxes removed

EO -- for the Appendix, label the table "Table A1" and include the heading "Appendix" at the top of the page. Change the citation in the text to "Appendix" instead of "Appendix 1"

A: corrected

EO -- Upload your high resolution figure files. Remove the figure # and caption from the figure. Only submit one version of each figure. Label each figure in the DESCRIPTION box on the upload screen as "Figure 1, Figure 2, etc." Include a "List of Figure Captions" after the References in your Manuscript file.

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EO -- Upload a "clean" version of your revised manuscript under the "Manuscript" category. If you wish to submit a "track changes" version, upload it under the "Revised Manuscript with Changes Highlighted" category

A clean version of the manuscript was uploaded.

Research Highlights

- The potential of upcoming L-band missions for biomass retrieval was investigated
- Polarimetry showed similar sensitivity to biomass levels as backscatter intensity
- Multi-temporal methods were more reliable when compared to single-date methods
- Significant improvements of biomass estimates were possible by increasing plot size

1 **Airborne Multi Temporal L-band Polarimetric SAR Data for Biomass Estimation in Semi-**
2 **Arid Forests**

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7 **Abstract**

8 Using the airborne Polarimetric L-band Imaging Synthetic aperture radar (PLIS) the impact of high revisit
9 cycle and full polarimetric acquisitions on biomass retrieval was investigated by means of backscatter-based
10 multi-temporal methods. Parametric and non-parametric models were used to relate reference biomass levels
11 obtained from field plot measurements and high point density lidar data to backscatter intensities or
12 polarimetric target decomposition components. Single-date retrieval using multiple independent variables
13 provided lower estimation errors when compared to models using one independent variable with errors
14 decreasing by 2% to 15%. The multi-temporal aggregation of daily biomass estimates did not improve the
15 overall retrieval accuracy but provided more reliable estimates with respect to single-date methods.
16 Backscatter intensities improved estimation accuracies up to 10% compared to polarimetric target
17 decomposition components. Using all four polarizations increased the estimation accuracy marginally (2%)
18 when compared to a dual-polarized system. The biomass estimation error was considerably reduced (up to
19 30%) only by decreasing the spatial resolution and was related to decreasing forest variability with
20 increasing pixel size. These results indicate that, at least in semi-arid areas, future L-band missions would not
21 significantly improve biomass estimation accuracy using backscatter-based modeling approaches despite
22 their better spatial resolution, higher revisit cycles and the availability of fully polarimetric information.

23 **1. Introduction**

24 The past decades have witnessed an unprecedented development of remote sensing techniques for land
25 monitoring. Passive sensors had a head start with the launch of the first Landsat satellite early in the 1970`s.
26 The development of active sensors such as synthetic aperture radar (SAR) was slower with the first missions
27 being launched in the early 1990s. The first space borne platforms carried single-band single-polarization

28 sensors with the European Remote Sensing (ERS) satellite, Japanese Earth Resource Satellite-1 (JERS-1)
29 and Radar satellite (RADARSAT-1) among the pioneer SAR satellites. The subsequent satellite-borne
30 sensors had improved characteristics, such as multiple polarizations, different acquisition modes, and higher
31 spatial resolutions. Recently, the use of SAR constellations has significantly increased the revisit cycle (e.g.,
32 Cosmo Sky-Med) or simultaneously acquired data with multiple spacecrafts (i.e., TerraSAR/TanDEM-X
33 mission). The increasing availability of SAR data has enabled research in numerous fields which has in turn
34 led to the development of diverse applications such as ship detection (Eldhuset 1996), earth displacement
35 measurements (Yague-Martinez et al. 2012), sea-ice mapping (Curlander et al. 1985), fire impact assessment
36 (Tanase et al. 2010a; Tanase et al. 2010b), land-use change detection (Tanase et al. 2009) and biomass
37 estimation (Dobson et al. 1992a; Englhart et al. 2011; Morel et al. 2011; Rignot et al. 1995; Robinson et al.
38 2013; Santoro et al. 2006; Tanase et al. in press).

39 Biomass estimation is undoubtedly one of the most pressing research topics currently, since information on
40 forest spatial distribution, biomass levels and dynamics is needed for accurate greenhouse gases flux
41 estimation, and thus policy development and implementation (Gibbs et al. 2007). The last two decades have
42 been strongly focused on the extraction of forest biomass estimates from SAR data, with the most recent
43 research employing L-band data due to its greater sensitivity to biomass levels and the data availability from
44 satellite missions such as JERS-1 and Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) Phased Array type L-
45 band Synthetic Aperture Radar (PALSAR) (Morel et al. 2011; Santoro et al. 2006; Santoro et al. 2009). The
46 potential of L-band radar backscatter to estimate aboveground biomass (AGB) has been studied for most
47 forest types, ranging from boreal to tropical regions using airborne and/or space borne sensors (Harrell et al.
48 1995; Imhoff 1995; Kasischke et al. 1995; Le Toan et al. 1992; Lucas et al. 2010; Pulliainen et al. 1999;
49 Santoro et al. 2006).

50 A number of biomass retrieval strategies were adopted including initially empirical (Harrell et al. 1997;
51 Lucas et al. 2000; Ranson et al. 1995; Sandberg et al. 2011), subsequently semi-empirical (Lu 2006;
52 Pulliainen et al. 1996; Santoro et al. 2006) and, more recently numerical (Burgin et al. 2011; Lucas et al.
53 2004) models. The empirical models have related radar backscatter to AGB using a range of functional
54 forms, including linear (Sandberg et al. 2011), logarithmic (Moreau and Le Toan 2003), exponential

55 (Englhart et al. 2011; Moreau and Le Toan 2003) and higher degree polynomials (Dobson et al. 1992b),
56 while semi-empirical models have frequently been based on the water cloud model (Attema and Ulaby
57 1978). Machine learning algorithms adapted to regression problems were also recently used for the retrieval
58 of bio-geophysical parameters from polarimetric SAR data (Neumann et al. 2012). Although consensus on
59 the best models for biomass retrieval is yet to emerge, parametric models are frequently used (Harrell et al.
60 1995; Harrell et al. 1997; Neumann et al. 2012; Robinson et al. 2013; Saatchi et al. 2007a; Saatchi et al.
61 2007b; Saatchi et al. 2011; Sandberg et al. 2011).

62 In recent years, polarimetric interferometry, tomography and polarimetric coherence tomography have been
63 used to estimate forest characteristics such as height or vertical structure (Cloude 2006, 2007; Cloude and
64 Papathanassiou 1998). Such methods have shown promising results but their implementation at wider scale
65 has remained limited due to the lack of suitable satellite sensors or observation scenarios (Garestier et al.
66 2008; Hajnsek et al. 2009; Tebaldini and Rocca 2012). Their potential also remains to be demonstrated over
67 a wide range of forest conditions and especially in semi-arid areas where trees are generally small and
68 significant penetration through canopy gaps occurs (Cronin 2004; Le Toan et al. 1992; Rignot et al. 1995).

69 L-band SAR sensors cannot measure biomass directly since the backscattered waves interact mostly with the
70 canopy layer (leaves/needles and branches), which contains only a fraction of the total tree biomass.
71 However, canopy biomass is often a reliable indicator of total tree biomass, allowing for indirect
72 relationships to be formed between radar and forest inventory data. Fully polarized radar datasets have the
73 advantage of enabling a complete description of the scattering process, thus providing information on the
74 entire scattering matrix which can be decomposed into ground, volume, and ground-volume contributions,
75 thus allowing some of the vertical forest structure to be retrieved. It is assumed that such information better
76 relates to forest biomass since the influence of the underlying ground is reduced for some of these
77 components. Coherent polarimetric decompositions can separate the scattering matrix into simpler scattering
78 responses. However, since the scattering matrix is only able to characterize pure scatterers, such
79 decompositions are less useful for the characterization of distributed scatterers, such as forests, due to the
80 presence of speckle noise. Forested areas are better characterized using second order (i.e., covariance or
81 coherency matrices) polarimetric representations through incoherent, model-based decompositions (Cloude

82 and Pottier 1996). The Freeman-Durden decomposition (Freeman and Durden 1998) was among the first
83 developed for separating three scattering components related to surface, double bounce and volume
84 scattering using physical models. A fourth component was later added (Yamaguchi et al. 2005) to
85 compensate for limitations in the Freeman-Durden model for areas with topographic slope. Recently, both
86 methods have been reformulated (Zyl et al. 2011) to avoid nonphysical negative powers obtained for some
87 polarization combinations.

88 In the near future new sensors with greater capabilities will be deployed, both to replace ageing/defunct
89 sensors, and to create new constellations. With the next generation L-band SAR sensors featuring improved
90 spatial resolution (down to 3 m in range and 1m in azimuth), higher revisit cycles (down to eight days), and
91 fully polarized acquisitions, there is a need to evaluate to what extent such capabilities could improve the
92 biomass estimation accuracy using current or novel (i.e., multi-temporal) backscatter-based modeling
93 approaches. Although a variety of polarimetric model-based decomposition techniques are currently
94 available, the limited availability of fully polarized datasets has restricted their use and validation under a
95 wide range of forest and environmental conditions. Similarly, limited availability of high temporal frequency
96 SAR datasets has restricted the development of multi-temporal biomass retrieval techniques based on dense
97 data series. Most polarimetric decomposition studies were undertaken for classification purposes (Dong et al.
98 2001; Maghsoudi et al. 2012; Trisasongko 2010) rather than direct biomass estimation (Gonçalves et al.
99 2011). To the knowledge of the authors, the use of specific scattering components for model
100 parameterization and direct biomass estimation has only been investigated recently (Neumann et al. 2012),
101 while biomass estimation from dense multi-temporal polarimetric SAR data series remains to be explored.
102 Consequently, the objectives of this study were to: i) evaluate whether improved forest biomass estimates
103 can be obtained from high temporal frequency SAR data as opposed to single date retrieval algorithms in
104 semi-arid environments, ii) investigate the use of polarimetric target decomposition components for direct
105 model parameterization, and iii) assess the impact of available polarizations and forest variability on the
106 biomass retrieval error.

107

108

109 2. Study area and ground data

110 The study area is located in the western plains of the Murrumbidgee catchment, a semi-arid environment,
111 near the township of Narrandera, New South Wales, Australia (Fig. 1). The area is characterized by
112 agricultural and grazing farms interspersed with forests. The precipitation is evenly distributed throughout
113 the year with a mean annual rainfall of 440 mm. The mean maximum temperature is 33° C and occurs in
114 January while the mean minimum temperature is 3° C and occurs in July. A small forest area, approximately
115 1800 ha in size, and dominated by white cypress pine (*Callitris glaucophylla*) with dispersed (10%) grey box
116 trees (*Eucalyptus microcarpa*) was the focus of this investigation. The topography is nearly flat with
117 elevation ranging from 140 m to 190 m and slopes being less than 5° for most of the forest.

118 A biometric survey was conducted using 60 circular plots (500 m² each, 12.62m in radius) clustered in 12
119 sites, with the data collected in September 2011 (Figure 1 and Appendix). A cluster site consisted of a central
120 plot with four surrounding plots whose centers were spaced at a distance of 35 m in the cardinal directions.
121 The GPS coordinates, diameter and height were recorded for 2251 trees with a diameter at breast height
122 (dbh) of 5 cm and above, whereas smaller trees were counted and only their average height recorded.
123 Information on grass cover and average height was also collected for 10 additional plots that have relatively
124 sparse vegetation. The biomass of the trunk, branches and leaves as well as the total AGB were estimated for
125 each tree using species-specific allometric equations (Burrows et al. 2001; Hamilton et al. 2005). These
126 values were subsequently aggregated to plot level. For white cypress pine both dbh- and height-based
127 allometric equations were considered. The only equations available for this species (Burrows et al. 2001)
128 were developed for the south-central Queensland region (1000 km north of the study area) which is
129 characterized by higher annual average precipitations (600 mm). Since the Burrows' models consistently
130 overestimated tree heights as a function of tree diameter for this study area (Fig. 2), the biomass values
131 obtained from dbh- and height-based allometric equations was averaged. The total AGB for individual plots
132 varied between 1.5 and 179.5 Mg ha⁻¹.

133 Ancillary information on soil moisture, soil roughness, wood density and leaf water content was also
134 collected during the field campaign for several sites. Soil moisture decreased from the beginning to the end
135 of the campaign by an average of 7% while leaf water content decreased by 30%. Trunk water content was

136 relatively stable (around 35%) during the second half of the campaign when such measurements were taken.
137 The average surface roughness was 0.7 cm with a standard deviation of 0.27 cm across eight sites where
138 measurements were taken using a 1-m long contact profiler.

139 **3. Remote sensing data**

140 The remote sensing data were acquired in the context of the Soil Moisture Active Passive Experiment
141 (SMAPEX), which was focused on providing airborne and ground data for algorithm development for the
142 upcoming NASA Soil Moisture Active Passive mission (Panciera et al. 2013). Although the SMAPEX
143 experiment consisted of three different field campaigns undertaken in 2010 and 2011, the forest survey and
144 over-flights were only carried out during SMAPEX3 (5-23 September 2011). The present study only uses
145 data from two of the sensors that acquired airborne information during these campaigns: the Polarimetric L-
146 band Imaging Synthetic aperture radar (PLIS) and the Riegl Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) Q560 (Hug et
147 al. 2004).

148 **3.1 SAR data**

149 The PLIS is a full polarimetric sensor with a radar frequency of 1.26 GHz which uses micro-strip antennas
150 mounted either underneath or on the wings of light aircrafts. Typically, PLIS operates between 300 and 3000
151 m aboveground level at aircraft speeds of 40-120 m/s with a pulse repetition frequency between 2-8 kHz.
152 Using a dual channel receiver both H and V polarizations are sampled simultaneously. The sensor
153 illuminates the ground on either side of the aircraft with an incidence angle varying from 15° to 45° across
154 the swath. Using a 30 MHz bandwidth, the single look slant range resolution is 6 m. The azimuth resolution
155 is 0.8 m. More information about the PLIS sensor is found in (Gray et al. 2011). During the SMAPEX3
156 campaign the sensor was flown over the study area nine times with a temporal frequency of two to three
157 days. However, in one of the flights (18 September 2012) the GPS timestamp over the forest was not
158 correctly recorded and the data could not be processed which left only eight days available for analysis
159 (Table 1). The sensor was flown at an altitude of 3000 m, giving a nominal ground swath of 2200 m on either
160 side of the aircraft.

161 The PLIS polarimetric calibration was accomplished using a modified version (Goh et al. 2007) of the
162 method described by (Ainsworth et al. 2006). The forest area was used as a distributed target to estimate
163 cross-talk parameters and cross-polarized channel imbalance while the co-polarized channels imbalance was
164 estimated from six Passive Corner Reflectors (PCRs) deployed in a nearby homogeneous grassland field.
165 Polarimetric calibrated data showed, over the PCRs, a mean ratio of the co-polarized channels of around 1
166 dB and a mean phase difference of 3° and 6° depending on the antenna. The absolute radiometric calibration
167 coefficient was estimated as the difference between the backscattering coefficients obtained from PCRs and
168 their theoretical radar cross-sections. After radiometric calibration, the difference between observed and
169 theoretical PCR cross sections were an average of 0.9 dB with a standard deviation of 0.8 dB.

170 The SAR metrics derived from PLIS observations were divided into two groups. The first group corresponds
171 to the backscatter intensity (BI) metrics which includes the intensity of the individual channels (i.e., HH, HV,
172 VH and VV). The second group corresponds to backscattering components obtained through polarimetric
173 target decomposition (TD). Pauli representation was used to separate the scattering matrix into simpler
174 scattering responses related to single bouncing (HH+VV), double bouncing (HH-VV) and volume (2HV)
175 scattering. By using incoherent polarimetric decompositions the coherency matrix was modeled as a function
176 of three scattering mechanisms; surface scattering, double-bounce or dihedral scattering, and volume
177 scattering (i.e., Freeman-Durden (Freeman and Durden 1998), Yamaguchi (Yamaguchi et al. 2005), and van
178 Zyl (Zyl et al. 2011)). In addition, an eigenvector-eigenvalue decomposition was used to generate the
179 entropy (H), anisotropy (A) and mean alpha angle (α) from the coherency matrix (Cloude and Pottier 1997).

180 To reduce noise, backscatter intensities were estimated after multi-looking in range and azimuth by 2 and 14,
181 respectively. The same factors were used to multi-look the coherency matrix. In addition, the coherency
182 matrix was filtered using a 5x5 window (Lee et al. 2006). The selected multi-look factors allowed for
183 obtaining a ground pixel spacing around 10 m. All SAR metrics were geocoded to the Universal Transverse
184 Mercator (UTM) coordinate system using a lookup table that described the transformation between the radar
185 and the map geometries (Wegmüller et al. 2002). The lookup table was generated using a digital elevation
186 model (DEM) and the flight information. To correct for possible inaccuracies in the input data, a refinement
187 of the lookup table was applied, in the form of offsets between the PLIS images and a reference image

188 mosaic derived from X-band SAR images provided by the Terrasar/Tandem-X mission. The geometric
189 accuracy of the single look slant range complex data from the Terrasar satellite, and by extension of the co-
190 registered Terrasar/TandemX product, was estimated to be better than 1 m (Fritz and Einder 2010; Nonaka
191 et al. 2008). High resolution representations of the backscatter intensity and van Zyl (van Zyl 2011) target
192 decomposition components are shown in Figure S2 and Figure S3 for the first day of the field campaign
193 (September 5th 2011).

194 3.2 Lidar data

195 Aircraft light detection and ranging (Lidar) acquisitions are useful for developing statistical or physically
196 based models to spatially extend local measurements (Goetz and Dubayah 2011). Lidar-based measurements
197 were used to provide enough samples across variable forest structures to facilitate the development of remote
198 sensing algorithms based on radar data. The full waveform-digitizing laser scanner Riegl Q560/240kHz was
199 flown over the forest area at an altitude of about 400m at the beginning and the end of the SMAPEX3
200 campaign. The system, recording all echo pulses within a small footprint (~15cm), was flown from two
201 different directions (N-S and E-W) with a 50% swath overlap that resulted in the same area of the ground
202 being covered four times. An average first return pulse density of 40 pulses per square meter (ppm) was
203 obtained after combining all flight lines. The Riegl software package RiAnalyze was used to extract discrete
204 returns from the raw lidar data. These returns were then combined with the navigation data to yield geo-
205 referenced point clouds. Accuracies of data resulting from this procedure are approximately 0.4 m
206 horizontally and 0.15 m vertically, with higher relative accuracies within individual scans. The point clouds
207 were then classed into ground and non-ground returns with all non ground returns being considered
208 vegetation since no human-made features were located within the forest perimeter.

209 4. Methods

210 The study was structured in three parts. First the forest inventory and point cloud Lidar data were used to
211 produce a reference biomass map. Second, backscatter intensities and polarimetric target decomposition
212 components from multi-temporal airborne acquisitions were used to retrieve biomass through parametric and
213 non-parametric modeling. Third, the influence of polarization and forest variability on biomass retrieval

214 errors was investigated. The use of a reference Lidar based biomass map was necessary from two reasons:
215 obtaining a representative number of samples for error analysis over the area covered by the airborne radar
216 sensor (i.e., some field plots were outside the SAR swath - Fig. 1 B and D panels) and obtaining plots of
217 variable size centered at the same coordinates for studying the effect of plot size and forest variability on
218 biomass estimation error. A flowchart (Fig. 3) is presented to make clear the methods used in this study. A
219 straight up analyses of field biomass and L-band airborne data was carried out recently within a comparative
220 study (Tanase et al. 2014). The study concluded that although Lidar data is overall twice as accurate when
221 compared to L-band SAR data, for some biomass intervals SAR data could provide fundamentally similar
222 results to Lidar when estimating forest biomass at high spatial resolution.
223 map

224 Canopy height is an important forest attribute that can be used as a predictor variable for parameters such as
225 biomass and forest volume (Lefsky et al. 2005; Nelson et al. 1988). However, lidar response to a forest
226 canopy is not only a function of tree height, but also a function of canopy closure and density; the latter
227 could be further used as a predictor of the forest structure and ultimately AGB (Arp et al. 1982; MacLean
228 and Krabill 1986).

229 Multiple linear regression was used to produce a spatially continuous biomass map using lidar metrics and
230 the field plots. Over 65 grid metrics were produced from lidar point cloud data at 5 m spatial resolution: i)
231 canopy closure at 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 m height, ii) canopy closure and forest density for specific strata
232 (i.e., 1-4, 1-6,1-8, 1-10,1-12, 1-16, 1-24, 2-4, 2-6,... 8-16, 8-24 m), and iii) overall metrics such as
233 maximum height, canopy surface area and volume under the canopy surface. Canopy closure metrics were
234 defined as the proportion of first returns over a specific height threshold. Strata specific canopy closure and
235 forest density metrics were defined as the proportion of first returns and respectively all returns falling within
236 specific height thresholds. The grid metrics were correlated with the ground-based plot information to select
237 an appropriate subset for biomass prediction. The selected grid metrics were used to derive spatially explicit
238 AGB estimates for the area covered by the lidar flight. Arcsine and log transformations were used to
239 normalize the distribution of the lidar-based metrics and the plot-based biomass, respectively. Since cross-
240 validated error magnitudes are far more valuable and indicative of true accuracy the regression

241 parameterization was performed using 75% of randomly selected sample data, with the remaining 25%
242 retained for validation (Goetz and Dubayah 2011). The calibration process iterated the dataset 10 times with
243 the dataset being randomly split into training and validation subsets to allow a robust estimation of the error
244 of the AGB reference map.

245 4.2 SAR based estimation of biomass from multi-temporal L-band data

246 Biomass estimation was undertaken by decomposing the PLIS polarimetric data into surface, double bounce
247 and volume contributions and subsequently using the metrics obtained within parametric and non-parametric
248 models. Although recent studies (Mitchard et al. 2009; Sandberg et al. 2011) showed that models based on
249 multiple polarizations (i.e., HH, HV, VV) do not significantly improve biomass estimation accuracy, it was
250 decided to corroborate these results for a significantly different environment characterized by relatively short
251 trees and low biomass levels. Previously, several models were investigated for the retrieval of biomass from
252 space borne L-band SAR data, starting from simple regression based parametric models to semi-empirical
253 water cloud-like models or non-parametric models (Tanase et al. in press). Since similar model types
254 provided comparable results it was decided to present only one model in each category (i.e., parametric and
255 non-parametric). The parametric models selected for biomass retrieval (Eq. 1 and 2) were modified from the
256 Sandberg et al. (2011) model by allowing for the effect of the incidence angle variation from near- to far-
257 range to be considered in the estimation. In this study, the average incidence angle at each sample plot was
258 included as a predictor variable.

$$259 \quad \sqrt{\text{AGB}} = a_0 + a_1 * \text{SARm}_1 + a_2 * \cos\theta \quad (1)$$

$$260 \quad \sqrt{\text{AGB}} = a_0 + a_1 * \text{SARm}_1 + a_2 * \text{SARm}_2 + a_3 * \text{SARm}_3 + a_4 * \cos\theta \quad (2)$$

261 where:

262 AGB – aboveground biomass (Mg ha^{-1})

263 $a_0 a_1 a_2 a_3 a_4$ – unknown model coefficients

264 SARm_x – SAR BI or TD metric (logarithmic scale)

265 θ – average local incidence angle at the sample plot

266 The non-parametric model selected to estimate AGB levels was the random forest (RF). Up to three SAR
267 metrics (e.g., HH, HH and HV, surface, dihedral and volume scattering, etc.) and the incidence angle were
268 executed in the RF model to retrieve biomass. RF regression (Breiman 2001) uses ensemble learning
269 methods by constructing a large number of decision trees from the training data which are subsequently used
270 to derive overall predictions as the average response from all individually trained trees.

271 After model parameterization and inversion, daily AGB estimates become available for each validation
272 sample and radar metric. Such daily estimates were viewed as different attempts to “guess” the biomass
273 level. Without *a priori* information it is impossible to determine which of these “guess” estimates are closest
274 to the real biomass levels. However, by aggregating daily AGB estimates one could decrease the uncertainty
275 in biomass estimation associated with the daily values. Several methods were used to combine the daily
276 biomass estimates by SAR metric: i) simple averaging (Da), ii) averaging only the values within 1.5 standard
277 deviations of the local mean and iii) weighted average with more weight being given to the dates showing
278 higher dynamic range from bare soil to dense forest. Since all of these aggregation methods provided very
279 similar values, only the results obtained for the simple averaging (Da) are presented in the following
280 sections. The aggregation of all daily biomass estimates obtained from the BI or TD metrics was also used to
281 obtain a final AGB value. The method involved averaging the biomass estimates obtained for all days and all
282 SAR metrics (Da-all) by metric type.

283 Biomass estimates based on multi-temporal (MT) data were obtained by i) simultaneously using all daily
284 backscatter values for a given SAR metric when parameterizing the RF model (MT-all) and by ii) averaging
285 daily backscatter into one unique multi-temporal value, by SAR metric, followed by the parameterization of
286 the various models (MT-ma). The coefficient of determination (R^2), the root mean squared error (RMSE) and
287 the relative RMSE (ratio between RMSE and mean biomass - $RMSE_{\%}$) were used to assess which SAR
288 metric and aggregation method is best suited for biomass retrieval.

289

290

291 4.3 Factors that influence biomass retrieval

292 Two factors influencing biomass retrieval from SAR system were investigated in this study: available
293 polarizations and the mapping unit area. Biomass estimation from fully polarimetric and dual polarized data
294 was evaluated by using BI metrics and the $RMSE_{\%}$ was compared. The $RMSE_{\%}$ was computed after
295 averaging all daily biomass estimates (Da-all) obtained from single parametric model inversion for the two
296 or four polarizations. In addition, the benefit of a full polarization sensor was further inferred by comparing
297 the R^2 , RMSE, and $RMSE_{\%}$ obtained for BI and TD metrics.

298 Random plots at various radii were used to assess the effects of mapping unit area to the AGB retrieval
299 accuracy. For forest biophysical characteristic retrieval from radar data the selection of an appropriate
300 estimation scale has major impacts related to decreasing radar speckle with increasing area and decreasing
301 forest heterogeneity. Such effects result in better estimations of the backscatter values and smaller forest
302 variability. SAR backscatter metrics and lidar-based biomass were extracted at corresponding locations using
303 10, 15, 25, 50, 75, and 100 m radius plots, which are equal to 0.003, 0.07, 0.2, 0.8, 1.8, and 3.1 ha,
304 respectively. The $RMSE_{\%}$ was related to forest variability expressed by the coefficient of variation for each
305 plot size. $RMSE_{\%}$ was computed by averaging all daily biomass estimates obtained from single parametric
306 model inversion (i.e., Da-all aggregation method).

307 5. Results

308 5.1 . Biomass reference map

309 For each forest stratum one lidar metric was retained to derive the biomass reference map (Figure 1 panel E
310 and Figure S1): the pulse density of the 1-12 m height stratum (D_{1-12}) was selected to describe the dense
311 understory layer while for the overstory layer the canopy percent cover in the 6-8 m height stratum (C_{6-8}) was
312 retained. As a general descriptor of the plot structure the volume under the forest canopy surface was used
313 (C_{vol}). This metric had the highest correlation with all biomass components and was always included as a
314 predictor variable by a stepwise regression analysis. At plot level, the error of the lidar-based biomass
315 reference map was estimated as 17.2 Mg ha^{-1} for average biomass levels of 60 Mg ha^{-1} . When analyzed at the
316 site level the error decreased to 13.2 Mg ha^{-1} . This decrease was explained by the lower forest variability at

317 such spatial scales, the higher confidence in the ground measured biomass aggregates, and the reduced effect
318 of the plot positioning errors.

319 5.2 SAR based estimation of biomass from multi-temporal L-band data

320 Although several parametric and non-parametric models were evaluated for biomass retrieval only results
321 obtained for models (1), (2) and RF are presented (Tables 2 and 3). Similarly, only results obtained for the
322 van Zyl polarimetric target decomposition method are presented since it provided the highest biomass
323 retrieval accuracy when compared to the remaining decomposition models (i.e., Freeman-Durden,
324 Yamaguchi and Cloude-Pottier) or the Pauli basis representation. A total of 131 random sample plots were
325 used to extract co-located lidar based AGB estimates and SAR BI and TD metrics for model
326 parameterization/validation. At 15 m radius the reference AGB for the selected random plots varied between
327 2.0 and 156.0 Mg ha⁻¹ with over 93% of them being below 100 Mg ha⁻¹. The mean plot biomass was 47.8 Mg
328 ha⁻¹ with a standard deviation of ±29.8 Mg ha⁻¹. At 100 m radius the maximum AGB was 120.2 Mg ha⁻¹.
329 The mean plot biomass was 50.0 Mg ha⁻¹ with a standard deviation of ±22.2 Mg ha⁻¹. Depending on the
330 flight day the estimated AGB ranged from 0.2 to 103.1 Mg ha⁻¹ with a mean value of 46.0 Mg ha⁻¹ when
331 using the fully polarized parametric model within single date retrieval for 15 m radius plots. For multi-
332 temporal retrieval through aggregation (i.e., Da) the estimated AGB ranged from 0.71 Mg ha⁻¹ to 88.2 Mg ha⁻¹
333 ¹. The daily temporal change of the retrieved biomass for three typical plots is shown in Figure 4.

334 For BI metrics Table 2 shows that daily RMSE_% can fluctuate up to 10% depending on metric selection and
335 modeling approach. The lowest daily difference, 2 to 4%, was observed for parametric models. Single metric
336 models showed roughly similar estimation errors while a marginal improvement of up to 2% was observed
337 for the model containing multiple polarizations. When using non-parametric models the selection of the SAR
338 metric played a more important role, with the maximum daily variation of the RMSE_% reaching 5 to 10%. In
339 addition, a model including multiple polarizations did not improve the estimation accuracy on a consistent
340 basis. Similar results were observed for TD metrics (Table 3). The main difference with respect to BI metrics
341 was the larger overall fluctuation, up to 15%, and the smaller difference, up to 1.5%, between models
342 containing one or several target decomposition metrics. Generally, TD metrics that related to volume
343 scattering mechanisms provided better results with higher R² and lower RMSE and RMSE_% being observed

344 when compared to using metrics related to dihedral and surface scattering. When comparing BI and TD
345 metrics results showed that BI metrics were generally more accurate when using parametric models, and less
346 accurate when using non-parametric models. The aggregation of the daily biomass estimates did not improve
347 the retrieval accuracy. However, it did provide more reliable estimates since the overall RMSE_% of the
348 biomass aggregates were close to the lowest daily RMSE_%. Finally, models based on multi-temporal data
349 (i.e., MT-all and MT-ma) did not improve the biomass estimation accuracy significantly, with RMSE_% being
350 close to the values obtained for some of the most accurate daily models.

351 5.3 Factors that influence biomass retrieval

352 The difference in relative error (Da-all aggregation method) when using PLIS full polarized data as
353 compared to only using two polarizations (i.e., HH and HV) is shown in Figure 5. The errors are shown for
354 plot sizes corresponding to the different extraction radii used. AGB estimation accuracy increased up to 0.5%
355 when using full polarized data especially for smaller plots. With increasing plot size the difference in AGB
356 estimation error decreases with dual polarized data reaching the same accuracy as fully polarized data for the
357 0.8 ha plot size.

358 The influence of the pixel size on the modeled relationships between HV polarization and AGB is shown in
359 Figure 6 while the relationship between the relative retrieval error and forest variability for different plot
360 sizes is shown in Figure 7. Forest variability was expressed by the coefficient of variation (CV) of the
361 reference AGB. A significant influence of the plot size was observed for all models and SAR metrics with
362 the estimation error decreasing according to increasing plot size. Depending on the plot size, SAR metric,
363 day and aggregation method the decrease varied between 10% and 30%. A very strong correlation ($R^2 =$
364 $0.95, p < 0.001$) between the AGB estimation error and forest variability was also observed (Fig. 6).

365 6. Discussion

366 Previous studies have shown biomass estimation errors from SAR data to be around 45 to 80% with respect
367 to the reference values (Harrell et al. 1997; Rignot et al. 1994; Sandberg et al. 2011). With the exclusion of
368 older stands or the selection of more homogeneous ones the estimation errors have been as low as 25% to
369 40% (Rignot et al. 1994; Santoro et al. 2006). This study has shown that AGB estimation errors can vary

370 between 30% and 50% in semi-arid areas depending on the spatial resolution at which the estimates are
371 needed. For relatively high spatial resolutions (i.e., 25 m) biomass estimation error reached 45% when using
372 backscatter intensity metrics, and increased by another 2-3%, when using polarimetric target decomposition
373 components or their linear combinations (e.g., ratio between volume and surface scattering). The analysis
374 showed that, in semi-arid areas, retrieval accuracy of forest biomass from L-band radar backscatter
375 observations is relatively stable, within 10%, for images acquired at short intervals and depends little on the
376 selected SAR metric (i.e., BI or TD) or modeling approach (i.e., parametric or non-parametric). It is noted
377 that during the airborne PLIS acquisitions moderate changes in soil moisture and canopy water content were
378 observed, with soil moisture decreasing by an average 7% and the leaf water content decreasing by an
379 average 30%. However, such changes were not systematically related to changes in biomass retrieval (Table
380 1 and Figure 4).

381 Neither the aggregation of daily biomass estimates nor the use of multi-temporal based models improved the
382 retrieval accuracy beyond the most accurate daily estimate for a given metric. However, *a priori* knowledge
383 of the true biomass value is not usually available since it is the quantity being estimated. By using
384 aggregation methods of multi-temporal data the average estimation error with respect to the worst daily
385 estimate improved by up to 5%. In addition, for 45% of the samples the daily estimates presented higher
386 errors when compared to the error recorded for the aggregated value. Therefore, multi-temporal data has the
387 potential to provide more reliable values with respect to single-date approaches. This could be especially
388 valid when variations of the environmental conditions are large, which was not the case in the current study.

389 Contrary to other studies (Harrell et al. 1997; Le Toan et al. 1992; Rignot et al. 1994; Sandberg et al. 2011)
390 slightly lower errors, 1-2% less, were obtained for the co-polarized channels as compared to the cross-
391 polarized channels. This could be attributed to the specific forest structure of this study area, which is
392 characterized by a relatively low height overstory layer and large gaps among tall trees. Such forest
393 structures coupled with the long L-band wavelength allow for greater canopy penetration by microwaves and
394 thus more interactions with the ground surface, to which the co-polarized channels are more sensitive.

395 Other studies (Sandberg et al. 2011) have shown that there is little to be gained when simultaneously using
396 co- and cross-polarized channels within a common model. The results of this study confirms such findings in

397 semi-arid environments, not only for parametric but also for non-parametric modeling approaches. An
398 average improvement of 3% in biomass retrieval accuracy, as observed by this study, provides little incentive
399 for acquiring fully polarized SAR datasets which usually come at the expense of spatial resolution or
400 coverage. Furthermore, model parameterization using polarimetric target decomposition metrics obtained
401 from fully-polarimetric data did not result in improved biomass estimation accuracies for our study area.
402 Special attention was given to polarimetric target decomposition metrics since both of the near-term L-band
403 missions, (i.e., ALOS PALSAR-2 and SAOCOM) will feature fully polarized sensors. The sensitivity to
404 biomass level was comparable between TD and BI metrics. Although produced for a different environment
405 and forest type, the results of the present study confirm the findings in (Neumann et al. 2012), which state
406 that L-band data produce better correlations with AGB from backscatter intensities than PolSAR-derived
407 metrics. However, it is noted that no attempt was made to use more advanced techniques such as polarimetric
408 interferometry. For L-band SAR data, polarimetric interferometry might provide better results when
409 combined with BI and/or TD metrics (Neumann et al. 2012).

410 It is well known that errors tend to decline with increasing plot size (Frazer et al. 2011; Mascaro et al. 2011;
411 Zolkos et al. 2013). Spatial averaging of the errors might contribute to this observation (Goetz and Dubayah
412 2011). However, this study shows that such observations are related to forest heterogeneity. With increasing
413 plot size, forest variability decreases which directly translates into lower estimation errors. Therefore, a
414 general rule of thumb regarding the optimum plot sampling size is far from straightforward since for highly
415 homogeneous forest such as plantations small plots sizes could be sufficient to capture the entire forest
416 structural variability. For remote sensing missions a 20% error is commonly employed as an objective
417 (Zolkos et al. 2013). Such an objective could be reached using radar backscatter-based modeling when forest
418 variability decreases below 40%. However, for such high accuracy to be achieved the sampling effort could
419 become substantial in highly heterogeneous forests.

420 Previous studies have demonstrated that at very coarse spatial resolutions (i.e., 1 to 10 km) the estimation
421 errors could reach 20-25% (Saatchi et al. 2007b; Santoro et al. 2011). Such accuracies are most probably
422 related to the significant reduction in forest variability expected at such spatial scales. The improvement of
423 goodness-of-fit/evaluative statistics associated with coarser spatial resolution must be interpreted cautiously,

424 however. There is an extensive body of literature on the modifiable area unit problem (MAUP) that arises
425 when analysis is undertaken at multiple spatial resolutions (Holt et al. 1996; Openshaw 1984; Unwin 1996).
426 Correlations among spatial phenomena regularly improve as pixel size increases. As noted, this is partly
427 related to the decrease in variability caused by averaging. It can also be related, however, to a decrease in the
428 number of observations such as occurs when 100 “small” pixels are compressed into 10 “big” pixels,
429 although this is less important if the number of big pixels remains large ($n = 50+$). Because of the MAUP,
430 interpretation of analytical results must be constrained to the pixel size used in the analysis.

431 The results of this study show that substantial improvements of the retrieval accuracy are possible at much
432 higher spatial resolutions (i.e., 150-200 m) by reducing the uncertainty of the reference biomass estimates,
433 the SAR metrics’ signal-to-noise ratio, and possible co-registration errors among datasets. Such
434 enhancements were possible by decreasing the spatial resolution of the input datasets which is equivalent to
435 increasing the radius of the plots used for data extraction from both the lidar-based reference map and the
436 geocoded SAR metrics. Thus, by increasing the plot size to approximately 3 ha (i.e., 175 m pixels) the forest
437 variability decreases by approximately 20% in our study area, which in turn facilitated a more accurate AGB
438 estimation, although the resulting estimates are only applicable to larger areas – i.e., at the coarser spatial
439 resolution as noted above. At such pixel size the biomass estimation error decreased to 30% from the more
440 than 50% recorded for 20 m pixels.

441 Relatively few studies (Robinson et al. 2013; Saatchi et al. 2011) have tried to assess forest variability and its
442 effects on biomass retrieval using radar data. Although both studies observed a decrease in RMSE with
443 increasing plot size they were somewhat limited by the low number of samples available within the
444 sensitivity-to-biomass interval of L-band. Saatchi et al. (2011) ascribed the decrease in RMSE to speckle
445 noise reduction and reduced geolocation errors. Although speckle and geolocation errors might affect the
446 biomass/backscatter relationship, we have shown that while speckle noise is relatively low (i.e., 42 looks for
447 10 m radius plots of PLIS data) the RMSE is still substantial. Robinson et al. (2013) recognized that the
448 sensitivity to AGB may improve at large spatial scales when effects of forest structure are averaged out. This
449 was demonstrated by the current study which has shown that even fine resolution SAR imagery contains
450 considerable noise which was mainly caused by inherent forest structural variability: 95% of the RMSE

451 errors encountered for decreasing plot size were explained by forest variability. Such noise can be eliminated
452 by decreasing the variability related to the sampling plots when products at lower spatial resolutions are
453 sufficient. However, high spatial resolution products sometimes are necessary, especially for highly
454 fragmented forest areas. Users of such research results must be aware of the trade-off between a stronger
455 relationship that is only applicable for large pixels (i.e., increased R^2 and decreased errors for larger mapping
456 area), or a weaker relationship and higher errors at a more spatially explicit scale.

457 In studies such as the present one, field data are commonly recorded for relatively small plots (<1ha) due to
458 labor costs and time constraints. Although not an objective, this paper demonstrated the value of having local
459 reference AGB estimates at the scale of observation required. In this study such estimates were obtained
460 from lidar data. The availability of lidar-based local AGB estimates assisted the retrieval algorithms,
461 providing sufficient data for both model parameterization and validation at different spatial resolutions. The
462 recent dismissal of NASA's Deformation, Ecosystem Structure and Dynamics of Ice (DESDynI) lidar
463 mission means that high quality lidar-based AGB estimates will not be available for future SAR missions.
464 This will hinder large-scale biomass retrieval since models calibrated with local data could provide better
465 retrieval accuracies than more universal models.

466 **7. Conclusions**

467 This paper studied the potential of upcoming L-band SAR missions to improve forest biomass retrieval
468 accuracy in semi-arid environments. Multi-temporal SAR data were acquired every two to three days over
469 three weeks using an airborne fully polarized L-band sensor. Parametric and non-parametric models were
470 calibrated to retrieve AGB from backscatter intensities and polarimetric target decomposition metrics within
471 single and multi-date retrieval approaches.

472 The most reliable biomass estimates were obtained when using multi-temporal data. However, the multi-
473 temporal biomass estimates did not improve the retrieval accuracy beyond the most accurate daily estimate.
474 Fully polarized systems improved biomass estimation accuracy only marginally over dual-polarized systems
475 when using backscatter intensity metrics. Polarimetric target decomposition-based retrieval showed similar
476 sensitivity to biomass levels as when using backscatter intensities. Overall, parametric models performed

477 slightly better for both single and multi-metric retrieval. The most significant improvement in biomass
478 retrieval accuracy was achieved by reducing the spatial resolution at which the estimates were produced. At
479 lower spatial resolutions the forest spatial variability reduces allowing for decreasing the estimation error to
480 up to 30%. The 1:1 relationship between forest variability and biomass estimation error has considerable
481 implications since even high spatial resolution sensors would not be sufficient to produce very accurate
482 biomass maps at fine scales (i.e., 10 or 20 m pixel size).

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- 685

686 List of Figure Captions

687 Figure 1 Study area (black square in panel A) and field data sampling locations (B) together with the airborne data
688 acquired by the PLIS (D) sensor. The inset (C) shows the separation of sampled plots at each site, the tree height and
689 the position of the trees measured in the field for an example site. Panels B and D have as the background a Landsat
690 ETM+ panchromatic image acquired on 24 October 2003. Panel E present the reference biomass map obtained from
691 filed plots and Lidar data through multiple regression.

692 Figure 2 Observed vs. predicted height for white cypress pine. The predicted height was computed as a function of dbh
693 using Burrows *et al.* (2001) allometric equations. The dashed line is the 1:1 line that indicates perfect agreement.

694 Figure 3 Flowchart of biomass retrieval from SAR data.

695 Figure 4 Daily temporal changes in biomass retrieval for three representative plots (3, 10 and 42) spanning the entire
696 biomass range.

697 Figure 5 AGB relative retrieval error (RMSE %) when using full and dual polarized PLIS data.

698 Figure 6 Influence of plot size on AGB estimation error for HV polarized PLIS data.

699 Figure 7 Relationship between relative retrieval error and forest variability (top). Observed decline in biomass
700 prediction error with decreasing spatial resolution (bottom).

701

702 Table 1. Acquisition dates of the SAR data and the cumulative precipitation (three days prior to acquisition) recorded at
 703 the closest meteorological station (Narrandera airport - 10 km north). Rainfall (mm) recorded during the SAR
 704 acquisition day is provided in parentheses.

Sensor	Day1	Day2	Day3	Day4	Day5	Day6	Day7	Day8
PLIS	05.09.2011	07.09.2011	10.09.2011	13.09.2011	15.09.2011	19.09.2011	21.09.2011	23.09.2011
Rainfall (mm)	0.2 (0.2)	3.6 (3.4)	1.6 (1.6)	1.6 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

705 Table 2. Indicators of biomass retrieval accuracy from backscatter intensity (BI) metrics (0.07 ha plots). Da and Da-all
 706 refer to different aggregation methods of daily biomass estimates (see Section 4.2). Multi-temporal (MT) refers to
 707 calibration of models using the average of the daily SAR metrics (MT-ma) while MT-all refers to calibration of random
 708 forest (RF) models by simultaneously using all daily values for a given SAR metric.

Model	SAR metric	Daily models and multi temporal averages of biomass estimates										MT-ma	
		Day1	Day2	Day3	Day4	Day5	Day6	Day7	Day8	Da	Da-all		
R^2													
(1)	HH	0.591	0.536	0.573	0.554	0.558	0.565	0.557	0.596	N/A		0.588	
	HV	0.542	0.529	0.528	0.524	0.537	0.535	0.568	0.577			0.567	
	VV	0.534	0.447	0.548	0.530	0.529	0.496	0.578	0.543			0.560	
(2)	HH,HV,VV	0.610	0.589	0.608	0.595	0.597	0.586	0.623	0.625	N/A		0.621	
RMSE (Mg ha ⁻¹)													
(1)	HH	21.2	22.7	22.2	22.5	22.4	22.3	22.6	21.1	21.8	21.5		21.7
	HV	22.9	22.7	23.1	23.2	22.8	23.0	22.2	21.7	22.3			22.3
	VV	22.9	22.5	23.2	23.1	22.8	23.1	22.1	21.7	22.3			21.9
(2)	HH,HV,VV	21.1	21.6	21.3	21.8	21.6	22.0	21.1	20.7	21.1	N/A		21.1
RMSE%													
(1)	HH	44.4	47.6	46.4	47.0	46.8	46.7	47.3	44.2	45.5	45.1		45.3
	HV	47.8	47.5	48.4	48.5	47.8	48.2	46.5	45.5	46.8			46.7
	VV	48.0	47.1	48.6	48.5	47.7	48.5	46.3	45.5	46.7			45.8
(2)	HH,HV,VV	44.2	45.3	44.7	45.6	45.2	46.1	44.2	43.4	44.2	N/A		44.1
Non-parametric RMSE%													
Daily models										MT-all		MT-ma	
RF	HH	47.6	55.0	54.4	55.4	54.6	53.0	55.0	51.9	44.3		50.5	
	HV	49.6	50.5	49.4	51.1	51.9	49.3	47.8	46.0	48.1		48.9	
	VV	46.3	48.7	48.4	46.8	47.0	48.3	44.6	49.3	45.8		45.0	
	HH,HV,VV	42.5	49.0	47.3	49.2	47.7	48.5	46.4	44.3	N/A		40.0	

709 Table 3. Indicators of biomass retrieval accuracy from target decomposition (TD) metrics (van Zyl decomposition, 0.07
 710 ha plots). Da and Da-all refer to different aggregation methods of daily biomass estimates (see Section 4.2). Multi-
 711 temporal (MT) refers to calibration of models using the average of the daily SAR metrics (MT-ma) while MT-all refers
 712 to calibration of random forest (RF) models by simultaneously using all daily values for a given SAR metric.

Model	SAR metric	Daily models and multi temporal averages of biomass estimates										MT-ma	
		Day1	Day2	Day3	Day4	Day5	Day6	Day7	Day8	Da	Da-all		
R^2													
(1)	Surface (S)	0.473	0.350	0.386	0.391	0.461	0.445	0.471	0.481	N/A		0.485	
	Double (D)	0.411	0.424	0.512	0.486	0.454	0.456	0.494	0.445			0.470	
	Volume (V)	0.518	0.500	0.506	0.521	0.504	0.496	0.509	0.519			0.514	
(2)	S, D,V	0.556	0.526	0.550	0.543	0.547	0.546	0.555	0.568	N/A		0.551	
RMSE (Mg ha ⁻¹)													
(1)	Surface (S)	23.0	25.3	24.9	24.9	23.3	23.5	23.6	22.8	23.0	22.7		23.2
	Double (D)	24.9	24.5	23.2	23.5	24.5	24.4	23.8	24.5	23.7			24.0
	Volume (V)	23.3	23.4	23.6	23.3	23.6	23.9	23.5	23.2	23.4			23.4
(2)	S, D,V	22.3	23.0	22.7	22.8	22.6	22.6	22.6	22.1	22.4	N/A		22.6
RMSE%													
(1)	Surface (S)	48.2	52.9	52.2	52.1	48.7	49.1	49.3	47.7	48.2	47.5		48.6
	Double (D)	52.2	51.4	48.5	49.2	51.4	51.2	49.8	51.2	49.6			50.3
	Volume (V)	48.8	49.0	49.4	48.8	49.3	50.0	49.3	48.6	49.0			48.9
(2)	S, D,V	46.7	48.2	47.4	47.8	47.3	47.4	47.3	46.2	46.9	N/A		47.3
Non-parametric RMSE%													
Daily models										MT-all		MT-ma	
RF	Odd (O)	49.2	53.3	52.4	50.5	49.6	52.4	48.3	50.5	50.6		51.6	
	Double (D)	57.0	57.4	51.0	56.3	58.8	55.4	52.0	58.1	53.6		54.2	
	Volume (V)	47.2	45.7	47.2	47.0	48.2	47.8	45.3	46.8	50.4		48.2	
	O, D,V	43.6	46.2	44.3	45.8	44.0	46.4	43.1	44.2	N/A		44.9	

713

714 Appendix

715 Table A1 Field plot data used for the estimation of the biomass reference map. Species proportion is rounded
716 to the nearest multiple of five. Mean trees dBH and height are computed only using trees not saplings.

717 Saplings refers to trees with dBH below 5 cm. Above ground biomass (AGB) refers to the sum of trees,

718 saplings and grass biomass. The center coordinates of the Gillenbah forest are 146.50° E, 34.81° S.

Site	Plot	Present species and their proportion (%)	Mean tree dBH (cm)	Mean tree height (m)	Number of trees	Number of saplings	Total AGB (Mg ha ⁻¹)
1	c	Ca (100)	42.6	14.9	5	0	69.5
1	e	Ca (90) Pi (10)	14.2	9.6	33	0	75.8
1	n	Ca (80) Eu (20)	20.6	10.7	14	0	74.2
1	s	Ca (90) Pi (10)	17.6	8.7	16	0	50.5
1	w	Ca (30) Eu (55) Pi (15)	42.4	18.3	7	0	143.8
10	c	Ca (75) Eu (25)	18.1	8.7	34	0	176.9
10	e	Ca (75) Eu (25)	15.6	8.5	15	430	52.7
10	n	Ca (80) Eu (20)	11.8	6.0	34	213	167.3
10	s	Ca (50) Eu (50)	10.7	7.4	10	354	24.1
10	w	Ca (95) Eu (5)	12.2	6.4	24	66	129.1
15	c	Ca (100)	14.9	8.5	23	28	70.8
15	e	Ca (100)	7.3	5.6	80	96	32.4
15	n	Ca (100)	20.6	9.9	18	111	86.0
15	s	Ca (100)	17.8	9.7	14	63	57.0
15	w	Ca (100)	8.4	5.7	44	115	55.3
17	c	Ca (90) Eu (10)	12.1	6.4	40	83	179.5
17	e	Ca (80) Eu (20)	12.5	6.7	34	0	55.0
17	n	Ca (100)	9.4	6.0	49	72	42.8
17	s	Ca (100)	9.5	6.1	47	29	39.1
17	w	Ca (100)	9.3	5.6	40	0	46.4
20	c	Ca (100)	7.3	4.9	47	21	18.3
20	e	Ca (95) Eu (5)	8.7	5.5	51	60	32.5
20	n	Ca (100)	9.2	6.0	65	72	50.6
20	s	Ca (100)	12.5	6.8	32	0	42.3
20	w	Ca (100)	9.0	5.8	65	88	53.7
23	c	Ca (100)	11.0	6.5	21	70	34.7
23	e	Ca (100)	7.3	5.5	93	99	36.8
23	n	Ca (100)	7.3	5.6	103	151	45.0
23	s	Ca (100)	15.0	6.3	9	30	16.4
23	w	Ca (100)	12.5	6.8	23	0	34.4
24	c	Ca (100)	10.6	6.7	55	0	47.8
24	e	Ca (100)	11.0	6.8	30	15	40.2
24	n	Ca (100)	13.4	7.5	36	0	55.9
24	s	Ca (100)	8.2	5.6	75	41	44.5
24	w	Ca (95) Eu (5)	13.5	7.7	30	2	52.2
30	c	Ca (100)	8.5	4.7	40	140	38.8
30	e	Ca (100)	8.2	5.4	67	165	41.0
30	n	Ca (100)	7.2	4.7	43	550	44.6
30	s	Ca (100)	9.1	5.2	42	165	44.2
30	w	Ca (100)	7.6	4.5	48	121	32.7
38	c	Ca (100)	13.6	7.5	37	80	62.1
38	e	Ca (100)	16.2	8.1	17	0	39.8
38	n	Ca (100)	13.2	7.3	24	0	39.3
38	s	Ca (100)	8.7	5.8	62	63	52.3
38	w	Ca (100)	8.0	5.1	57	45	36.7
42	c	Ca (100)	6.8	5.0	68	38	22.2
42	e	Ca (100)	8.7	5.5	53	86	43.9
42	n	Ca (100)	7.1	4.9	51	68	25.8
42	s	Ca (100)	7.2	5.2	53	163	24.6
42	w	Ca (100)	6.8	4.9	36	420	27.9
67	c	Ca (100)	16.2	9.7	33	0	75.8
67	e	Ca (100)	17.5	8.8	23	10	76.5
67	n	Ca (100)	10.2	6.0	47	99	49.6
67	s	Ca (100)	9.9	6.4	53	26	36.9
67	w	Ca (100)	11.1	6.8	43	56	59.1

99	c	Ca (85) Eu (15)	15.5	9.6	37	47	143.1
99	e	Ca (90) Eu (10)	15.6	9.2	29	55	87.7
99	n	Ca (70) Eu (30)	22.0	11.6	24	61	152.1
99	s	Ca (100)	12.1	7.8	49	20	56.4
99	w	Ca (100)	13.8	7.1	19	30	35.8

719

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